

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 7.5

Report of Briefing Meeting to inform MEPs and European Officials on Arctic topics of emerging priority (T7.3)

Version 1

23-February-2024

101003472 | Arctic Passion

**ARCTIC
PASSION**

Work package

7 – Supporting coherent policy
and decision making

Lead beneficiary

1 - EPB

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Status

Project Coordinator accepted

Dissemination level

Public

This project has received funding from the
European Union's Horizon 2020 research and
innovation programme under grant
agreement No. 101003472

Title page:

Report on Policy Briefing

Deliverable D7.5

ARCTIC PASSION

Arctic PASSION is co-funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101003472 and by the Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research

<https://ocean-ice.eu/>

About this document:

Deliverable: D7.5 Report of Briefing Meeting to inform MEPs and European Officials on Arctic topics of emerging priority

Work Package: WP 7, Task 7.3: Dialogue with the EU Parliament and the EC

Delivery date: 31 January 2024 (month 15)

Type of document: Report

Dissemination level: Public

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Cover sheet: Photo credit to Renuka Badhe (EPB)

Table of contents

Title page:	1
1.1 Executive summary and introduction	4
1.2 Structure of the report	4
2. Core	4
4. Impact.....	7
4.1 Contribution to the project objectives and key exploitable results.....	7
4.2 Policy relevance.....	8
4.3 Communication, Dissemination and Publications.....	10
5. Reference documents	11
Annexes	12

1.1 Executive summary and introduction

As part of the dissemination and outreach activities enumerated in Work Package 7 of the EU-funded Horizon Europe Arctic PASSION project, the European Polar Board (EPB) organised a policy briefing to highlight the work, goals, and relevance of emerging Arctic priorities identified by Arctic PASSION to the public. The event was titled

“The Changing Poles: how Antarctic and Arctic science helps to inform and prepare the EU for changes in sea level rise and the global climate”.

The event was held in the European Parliament’s main building on 24 January, 2024 from 14:15 to 16:00 CET. **The main message of the policy briefing was to raise the profile of the project, as well as to signpost project progress, expected outcomes, links to EU policy priorities and underline the need for sustained polar observing systems to enable well-informed decision making.** The policy briefing was held in-person and online. As such, the policy briefing’s main audience was the European Institutions, and several high-profile EU decisionmakers were speakers. The policy briefing was streamed online, ensuring a wide reach and dissemination.

The event was co-organised with two other partners. The first was the OCEAN:ICE project, an EU-funded polar research project focused on ocean-cryosphere exchanges in Antarctica and its impacts on the climate and the earth system and, like Arctic PASSION, a member of the EU Polar Cluster. The second partner was the European Bureau for Conservation and Development, which manages the European Parliament Intergroup on Climate Change, Biodiversity and Sustainable Development, and which assisted in booking the venue and speakers for the event. The European Polar Board organised the event as part of its deliverable and on behalf of the Arctic PASSION project. This combination of partners provided a unique and well-attended event focused on a bi-polar perspective and the relevance of EU-funded polar research to broader EU policy.

The keynote speakers were Arctic PASSION Project Coordinator Dr. Michael Karcher (AWI) and a shared presentation of OCEAN:ICE Project Coordinator Dr. Ruth Mottram (DMI), OCEAN:ICE initiator and Senior Scientist Dr. Andrew Meijers (BAS). Opening and closing remarks were given by MEP Urmas Paet, who was hosting the event. MEP Paet is Co-Chair of the Arctic Working Group of the European Parliament Intergroup on ‘Climate Change, Biodiversity and Sustainable Development’. A panel was convened for the second half of the event with the Head of Unit for ‘Healthy Ocean & Seas’ DG RTD Elisabetta Balzi, EU Arctic Envoy Clara Ganslandt, and Head of Greenland’s Mission to the EU Inuuteq Holm Olsen. The panel was moderated by the keynote speakers.

The policy briefing can be considered a success based on several factors. Attendance was high and included officials from the European Institutions, other EU-funded projects, and other interested academics and civil society stakeholders. The event was held in a hybrid format, with about 20 attendees in person and 89 attendees online.

1.2 Structure of the report

The report is divided in an outline of performed work leading up to the policy briefing, referenced documents, results, impact and annexes.

2. Core

3.1 Methods

See 3.4, as this is combined with the timeline.

3.2 Results

The policy briefing's main objective was to raise the profile of the Arctic PASSION project and communicate OCEAN:ICE results. This was accomplished through a dialogue with and presentation to several high-level European stakeholders. This allowed the project's relevance and expected results to be put forth in policy-relevant detail.

The policy briefing can be considered a success based on several factors. Attendance was high and included officials from the European Institutions, other EU-funded projects, and other interested academics and civil society stakeholders. The event was held in a hybrid format, with about 20 attendees in person and 89 attendees online. The audience consisted of policy makers and governmental representatives (40% together), representative of the civil society (NGOs 6%) and private businesses (5%). We also had a large number of representatives of research networks and academia (49%). This represented a very engaging intersection of Arctic and Antarctic stakeholders, representing the European institutions, national stakeholders, and polar scientists.

Fig 1: Composition of the audience

The audience had the opportunity to ask questions to the speakers and panellists.

The keynote speakers asked prepared questions of the panellists as well. This led to a robust engagement between Arctic PASSION and top EU decision-makers, as well as with the wider public.

The event was also a success in that it involved another EU-funded Horizon2020 research project (OCEAN:ICE), allowing a discussion on common issues and promoting the image of the European Union as a substantial contributor to research in both poles. Several EU initiatives were referenced by the speakers, including the EU Polar Cluster, the upcoming European Polar Coordination Office, the European Space Agency, and several other EU-funded projects.

The policy briefing itself provided an opportunity to engage on the topic of Arctic observing systems' role in EU policymaking and priorities. The project leaders' presentations, the statements from the panellists and the questions, and interventions featured the EU's role in Arctic and future opportunities for engagement along current policy-lines. By linking Arctic PASSION's focus pan-Arctic observations with OCEAN:ICE's focus on Antarctica and the Southern Ocean, the projects complemented one another and provided a complete picture of EU-funded polar research and priorities.

3.3 Discussion

The format of the policy briefing allowed for scientific talks, political interventions, and discussion and so allowed for substantial exchanges. Many of the speakers and audience members expressed a desire for more frequent events of this sort.

Main outcomes of the discussion:

1. The importance of long-term, sustained funding for polar observations. Both Arctic PASSION and OCEAN:ICE emphasized the critical importance of funding that extends beyond project lifetimes, and supports polar observations in more scientifically relevant timescales – decades or more.
2. The direct links between the polar regions and European and global climate security. Both extreme weather events and sea level rise threaten European social, economic, and environmental health. The research being done at the poles and the predictions and models that arise from this are essential to understanding and planning for these impacts.
3. The need for continued EU engagement in the region. Clara Ganslandt described the ambition of the EU to increase its presence in the Arctic and Antarctic regions, following current strategy and policy layouts. This includes the need to continue funding polar research and encouraging and facilitating international cooperation in the sciences and beyond. Elisabetta Balzi added that the EU already funds many polar research projects, and is planning many more.
4. Involvement of local stakeholders. Inuuteq Holm Olsen spoke about the Greenland's recent National Research Strategy and the need for research to benefit local stakeholders through involvement and outcomes. This was supported by both projects.

3.4 Timeline

The main Deliverable work was divided into three phases.

- Q1 and Q2 of 2023: The first phase consisted of outlining the shape and agenda of the policy briefing and finding relevant partners for the sake of visibility and scale. We settled on partnering with the OCEAN:ICE project due to their similar task of presenting polar science findings and recommendations to the European Parliament. We also established a relationship with the European Bureau for Conservation and Development (EBCD), a Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) founded in 1989 and based in Brussels (Belgium), which specialises in gathering Members of the European Parliament for discussions around similar scientific and environmental topics. A series of meetings between partners established the project roles, timeline, and overall objectives of the policy briefing.
- Q3 of 2023: The second phase included fine-tuning messages to be presented. This coincided with the drafting of a Concept Note, which went through several iterations and rounds of feedback from both projects. Arctic PASSION dedicated a special action group of Arctic PASSION representatives to this, who jointly worked on the concept note and brought in perspectives from their Work Packages. Their attendance ensured most Work Packages of Arctic PASSION were collaborated with for D7.5.
 - Michael Karcher
 - Margareta Johansson

- Volker Rachold
- Janet Pawlak
- Vito Vitale
- Adriaan Perrels
- Øystein Godøy
- Johanna Roto
- Renuka Badhe
- Griffith Couser
- Pjotr Elshout
- Sabrina Heerema
- Luisa Cristini
- Gosia Smieszek-Rice
- Jeremy Wilkinson

This was then publicly disseminated by all three partners. This Concept Note gave a broad introduction to the projects and the major topics to be covered, and served as a ‘teaser’ for the potential audience. Shortly after this was released, registrations for in-person and online participation began.

- Q4 of 2023: The third phase consisted of drafting the Policy Brief, a document that served to summarize and enhance the topics discussed during the policy briefing itself. This document went through multiple iterations and was expanded and filled out following multiple meetings between the project partners. This honed the message further, focusing it on the challenges and recommendations which have become apparent from the work of the projects. This flyer was then published and served as a background to the policy briefing, and as an enduring product which will continue to be available for public distribution.
- Q1 of 2024: Lastly, the policy briefing itself and the presentation preparations and review concluded the work performed on the event. This included a panel with pre-prepared questions, an intervention by our host MEP Urmas Paet, and the two keynote scientific talks. Work following the event itself includes wrap-up, collecting all materials to be put online, and the deliverable report.

4. Impact

4.1 Contribution to the project objectives and key exploitable results

The main aim of Arctic PASSION is to co-create and implement a Pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems (pan-AOSS), which requires a well-integrated methodological framework. This policy briefing contributed to the main aim of Arctic PASSION at it raised awareness at the EU Parliament level on the importance of sustained capacity to build and operate such a system. It underlined the need for (Arctic and Antarctic) observations to provide decision makers with appropriate information to develop well-informed policies.

The main result of this policy briefing that awareness was raised at the designated stakeholders (EU policy makers and MEP’s) to focus on sustained polar observations, climate change and the Arctic PASSION project.

The flyer developed for this briefing (see annex) can be used to continue raising awareness for the coming year. The messages, recommendations and actions identified in the flyer will be relevant for several years, as they point at longer-term processes.

The knowledge on how to organise a policy briefings at high level places might be useful internally for the Arctic PASSION project for any further policy briefings, if any.

4.2 Policy relevance

The event comes in the context of rising political importance for both poles. While the Arctic is a more direct geopolitical priority for the EU, the Antarctic is becoming a relevant area of engagement as well. This is emphasised by recent European Parliament resolutions, including the formation of a Friends of the Arctic group by MEP Urmas Paet, host of the event. The recently released “Joint Communication on a stronger EU engagement for a peaceful, sustainable and prosperous Arctic”, and the European Parliament-commissioned report “Antarctica: What role for the European Union?” are further evidence of the increasing need for building awareness of and engagement with ongoing polar research and experts.

Together with Arctic Passion, OCEAN:ICE drafted several of the recommendations which were shared in the briefing document and were delivered in the format of solutions to current challenges. For the sake of this report, the topic, challenge, and solutions are listed.

Long-term funding to support knowledge-based decision-making

- Challenge: A lack of long-term financial and political support for polar observations and information services which serve the needs of local inhabitants, science and policymakers globally.
- Calls for: Sustained support for long-term observations and information services based on the needs and requirements of inhabitants, stakeholders, and scientists by supporting actions initiated by the European Parliament and the European Commission.

Integrated Southern Ocean and Antarctic observing system

- Challenge: The present observational network in the Antarctic and Southern Ocean is ad hoc, has significant spatial and technical gaps and struggles to maintain ‘baseline’ coverage.
- Calls for: Sustained funding and political support for long term observations, the development and deployment of enabling technologies, and support for the implementation of the Southern Ocean Observing System future observing network.

Integrated Arctic observing system

- Challenge: The present Arctic observing system is too fragmented and there is no clear governance structure.
- Calls for: Sustained funding and political support by the European Union for better coordination of pan-Arctic Ocean observations and the dissemination of relevant data.

Inclusion of Indigenous Peoples and local communities

- Challenge: Limited inclusion of Arctic Indigenous Peoples and local communities.
- Calls for: Changes in the funding and decision-making structure for a more equitable and inclusive Arctic observing system

Implications of geo-politics on Arctic science

- Challenge: The current geopolitical situation prevents access and collaboration on a pan-Arctic scale.
- Calls for: To become more resilient to changes in the collaboration of states.

Accessibility and standardisation of data

- Challenge: The lack of easy access to data, as well as the inability to integrate datasets (data interoperability) to develop meaningful information services.
- Calls for: An agreed framework for harmonised data and the enhancement of data-interoperability and accessibility.

Sustainable development goals

The policy briefing touched on nearly all SDGs:

Climate neutrality	[Full relevant]	Sea Level Rise, a primary research objective, is a direct result of greenhouse gas emissions, and any addressing of SLR must address climate neutrality as well.
Clean Water and Sanitation	[Partially relevant]	SLR has the potential to inundate and infiltrate freshwater aquifers, treatment plants, and sewage systems, reducing water quality and availability for coastal communities.
Life Below Water	[Full relevant]	While not a major topic for this policy briefing, the warming oceans are of critical importance to marine biology.
Life on Land	[Partially relevant]	Coastal flooding and weather pattern changes driven by polar warming will have indirect effects on land-based life.
No Poverty	[Partially relevant]	Economic costs associated with a lack of preparedness and damage from coastal flooding and SLR will imperil the livelihoods of millions.
Decent Work and Economic Growth	[Partially relevant]	SLR and associated climate change effects will have negative physical and economic impacts on coastal communities. However, as was pointed out on the panel, this will also expose new areas for commercial utilisation.
Affordable and Clean Energy	[Partially relevant]	Connected to climate neutrality, clean energy is critical to mitigating SLR.

Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	[Partially relevant]	Coastal infrastructure will need to be refitted, refurbished, and expanded to mitigate the worst effects of SLR.
Sustainable Cities and Communities	[Full relevant]	Sustainable cities depend on accurate forecasting for extreme weather events, SLR, and other climate-driven impacts. The ability of cities to address these impacts is a key factor in addressing the effects of climate change globally, especially given the increasing urbanisation in most countries, including Arctic areas. SLR models, arguably, impact coastal cities most of all.
International cooperation	[Full relevant]	In Antarctica, which has no national jurisdiction, international cooperation is of supreme importance to effectively set up and maintain observing systems and research on the continent and in the Southern Ocean. Positive international cooperation and strengthening of adjacent institutions is crucial for the long-term benefit of the continent, and with the robust and diverse scientific work arising from such a situation, international cooperation thus benefits the globe at large.

4.3 Communication, Dissemination and Publications

Communication before the event was handled via all event partners: EPB, OCEAN:ICE, Arctic PASSION, and the EBCD. The EBCD led on generating advertising materials, including handling registration for the event itself.

Event promotion began on 15 September 2023 with the drafting of the Concept Note (Annex 1). This Concept Note was distributed through selected contacts, who were encouraged to further distribute it to interested parties. The Concept Note served as the basis for the event website: <https://ebcd.org/events/hybrid-event-from-changing-polar-regions-to-policy-responses-strengthening-eu-and-global-climate-preparedness/>

The event was advertised via X through the EPB (@eupolarboard), OCEAN:ICE (@OCEANICE_EU), Arctic PASSION (@arctic_passion), the EU Polar Cluster (@EUPolarCluster), and the EBCD (@EBCD_bxl).

The event was also advertised on LinkedIn by the EPB, OCEAN:ICE, and Arctic PASSION.

The event was advertised on Facebook by the EPB, OCEAN:ICE, Arctic PASSION, and the EU Polar Cluster.

The event was advertised on Mastodon by the EPB.

The advertisements almost exclusively reposted the event banner generated by the EBCD (Annex 2) with relevant commentary by the project / organisation.

Social media engagement was largely in line with other posts on all channels. The event was first advertised to raise interest, and following the opening of registration on 5 December, the registration link was disseminated through all available channels.

The flyer has been distributed to all project partners and was available for those attending in-person at the event. An online copy will be linked from all project websites and is hosted at Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/10521785>

As mentioned, the event was livestreamed via a link sent to all those who registered online participation. A recording of the event is available on the event website: <https://ebcd.org/events/hybrid-event-from-changing-polar-regions-to-policy-responses-strengthening-eu-and-global-climate-preparedness/> and will soon be available on all project partner YouTube channels.

5. Reference documents

The policy briefing resulted in two main documents:

- The policy brief with key messages and project descriptions is fully public via Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/10521785>. The policy brief was handed out in physical copies to in-person participants.
- Agenda of the briefing: <https://ebcd.org/events/hybrid-event-from-changing-polar-regions-to-policy-responses-strengthening-eu-and-global-climate-preparedness/>
- A recording of the event will be hosted on the EPB YouTube channel: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCBZM37I_50Hb0g2AYcgqAsg and on project websites.
- The presentations Arctic PASSION and OCEAN:ICE presented at the event:
Presentation by OCEAN:ICE: DOI <https://zenodo.org/records/10581017>
- Presentation by Arctic Passion: DOI [10.5281/zenodo.10600062](https://zenodo.org/records/105281).
- An event report will be prepared by the EBCD to summarize the day itself, and will be soon available on the EBCD webpage: <https://ebcd.org/events/hybrid-event-from-changing-polar-regions-to-policy-responses-strengthening-eu-and-global-climate-preparedness/>

Annexes

Annex 1: Concept Note

OCEAN:ICE, Arctic PASSION, European Polar Board Policy Briefing Concept Note

Title: From Changing Polar Regions to Policy Responses: Strengthening EU and Global Climate Preparedness

Location: European Parliament

Date: Mid/Late January 2024

This event will showcase the latest findings of [OCEAN:ICE](#) and [Arctic PASSION](#) on how changes in the polar regions impact European climate, infrastructure and livelihoods. Both the Arctic and Antarctic play a pivotal role in regulating the global climate. Changes at the Poles are having direct impacts on communities around the world. In Europe, an increased number of recent extreme events has shown the urgency of mitigation and adaptation strategies that are based upon multiple disciplines and knowledge systems.

Advancing polar scientific research and well-coordinated observations, dissemination and open access to knowledge are key components of the decision making process. This is emphasised by recent [European Parliament resolutions](#). As attention in Europe and across the globe turns increasingly towards the Poles, European projects including OCEAN:ICE and Arctic PASSION aim to present/illustrate status and implications of their current research and observation activities to highlight impacts on the European Union and beyond.

The work of both projects will contribute to future EU engagement with the polar regions and inform future EU policy and are relevant to the recently released "[Joint Communication on a stronger EU engagement for a peaceful, sustainable and prosperous Arctic](#)", and the European Parliament-commissioned report "[Antarctica: What role for the European Union?](#)"

OCEAN:ICE is co-funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for Research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation.

Arctic PASSION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101003472.

Further information regarding the Organising team:

The **OCEAN:ICE** project focuses on understanding how the Antarctic Ice Sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate. The data and models of the project will ultimately be able to reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic Ice Sheet will melt in the near and far future, and provide information about potential tipping points, changes to sea level rise, and the potential impacts of sea level rise on European coastal areas.

Arctic PASSION aims to contribute to the international effort for the co-creation and implementation of a more coherent, integrated Arctic observing system. Main actions include to extend and better coordinate pan-arctic observations to close gaps and overcome fragmentation, to strengthen inclusion of science, Indigenous and local knowledge, to streamline access to and interoperability of Arctic data, and to develop services tailored to Arctic stakeholders and right holders' needs.

European Polar Board is an independent organisation focused on major strategic priorities in the Arctic and Antarctic. EPB Members include research institutes, logistics operators, funding agencies, scientific academies and government ministries from across Europe.

Annex 2: Online Advertisement Banner

FROM CHANGING POLAR REGIONS TO POLICY RESPONSES - STRENGTHENING EU AND GLOBAL CLIMATE PREPAREDNESS

24 JANUARY 2024
14:15 - 16:00 CET
HYBRID EVENT:
EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT
ROOM: ASP 5G1 / ONLINE

HOSTED BY MEP URMAS PAET

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Annex 3: Final Agenda**FINAL AGENDA:**

- 14:00 – 14:15:** Welcome of participants – Networking coffee
- 14:15 – 14:25:** Opening remarks by **MEP Urmas Paet**
- 14:25 – 14:50:** Presentations by:
- **Dr. Michael Karcher**, Project Coordinator of Arctic PASSION and Senior Scientist at the Alfred Wegener Institut
 - **Ruth Mottram**, Project Coordinator of OCEAN:ICE, Danish Meteorological Institute and the initiator of OCEAN:ICE, and **Andrew Meijers**, Senior Scientist at British Antarctic Survey
- 14:50 – 15:20:** Panel discussion with the participation of:
- **Elisabetta Balzi**, Head of Unit 'Healthy Ocean & Seas' (RTD.B.4), DG RTD, European Commission
 - **Clara Ganslandt**, Special Envoy for Arctic matters, European External Action Service (EEAS)
 - **Inuuteq Holm Olsen**, Head of Mission / Minister Counsellor, Greenland Mission to the EU
- 15:20 – 15:50:** Q&As with the audience
- 15:50 – 16:00:** Closing remarks by **MEP Urmas Paet**

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